

Deliverable D1.5

**Database of assessments of
implementation and impact
indicators**

Imprint

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MERLIN Key messages

- 1. The aim of the MERLIN Database of assessments of implementation and impact indicators is to make the data of the MERLIN impact monitoring across the 18 restoration cases studies generally available.**
- 2. This deliverable marks the open access publication on Zenodo of contextual data for the case studies as well as data reported by each of the case studies across the 13 European Green Deal (EGD) policy areas, totalling 14 CSV file uploads.**
- 3. Each of the 14 uploads has an individual DOI.**
- 4. Storage in the Zenodo Data Repository allows uncomplicated and open use of the MERLIN Restoration Case Study assessment data to enable future analyses.**

MERLIN Executive Summary

This deliverable documents the successful completion of data production and publication with respect to the MERLIN Database of assessments of Implementation and Impact indicators.

Raw data from the impact monitoring within the EU Horizon 2020 project MERLIN (grant agreement No. 101036337) is reported for each case study to May 2025. These data have been compiled in common formats and uploaded to the Zenodo Data Repository. In total, the following 14 uploads were completed:

- Context data, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17119631
- Data of the Biodiversity Net gain criterion, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17119733
- Data of the Climate regulation criterion, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17119850
- Data of the Flood resilience criterion, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17119895
- Data of the Drought resilience criterion, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17119954
- Data of the Health and well-being criterion, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17119982
- Data of the Zero pollution criterion, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17120025
- Data of the Farm to fork criterion, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17120070
- Data of the Sustainable energy criterion, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17120114
- Data of the Sustainable transport criterion, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17120150
- Data of the Inclusive participation and governance criterion, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17120183
- Data of the Circular economy criterion, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17120221
- Data of the Financing the transition criterion, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17120279
- Data of the Green growth criterion, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17120323

All files were uploaded in CSV format ensuring a high compatibility for end users.

Storage in the Zenodo Data Repository allows consistency with other MERLIN data publications and provides open access to the wider community to support future analyses.

We provide a DOI for each individual data set allowing integrity in citation tracking in their use beyond the project lifetime.

Content

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1 Introduction

The MERLIN Database of assessments of Implementation - and Impact Indicators provides open access to the wider community to the raw data provided by each of the 18 MERILN case studies up to end of May 2025. These data were collated by a team of data managers and are presented in a common format. This report marks the publication of these data resources on the Zenodo Data Repository and provides the information required to access them.

The data were collated by case study leads following a systemic assessment and reporting approach, the MERLIN Monitoring and Assessment Framework, with guidance from the coordination team of MERLIN WP1. The data have been analysed and synthesised to provide a high-level assessment of restoration impact in MERLIN Deliverable 1.6, summarised in digital form on the project website in MERILN Deliverable 1.4.

This report documents the basic information required to access the MERLIN Database of assessments of implementation and impact Indicators through the Zenodo Data Repository.

2 Online database

2.1 Basic information

The data files are saved in the Zenodo research repository (<https://zenodo.org/>). During the MERLIN impact monitoring the case studies provided context data as well as monitoring data on 13 European Green Deal (EGD) policy areas. For the context data and each of the EGD policy areas an individual upload to Zenodo was completed producing 14 data uploads, each with an individual DOI.

Before uploading, each file was anonymised and saved in CSV format in order to guarantee a broad compatibility with data analysis and storage applications. These data products are listed in Section 2.2.

2.2 Contents

The individual file uploads for the MERLIN Database of assessments of implementation and impact indicators are summarised in Table 1. Each upload contains CSV format raw data submitted by the case studies and compiled together to provide a full list of submitted data for all case studies for each EGD policy area criterion.

Table 1 - dataset title, description, size and DOI for the 14 Zenodo uploads of the MERLIN Database of assessments of implementation and impact indicators.

Title of dataset	Description	Size	DOI
Impact monitoring raw data reported by case studies in MERLIN (EU Horizon 2020) - Context data	This dataset contains csv files with raw data of the impact monitoring within the EU Horizon 2020 project MERLIN (grant agreement No. 101036337) reported by case studies till end of May 2025 as Context data.	272.69 KB	10.5281/zenodo.17119631
Impact monitoring raw data reported by case studies in MERLIN (EU Horizon 2020) - Biodiversity net gain	This dataset contains csv files with raw data of the impact monitoring within the EU Horizon 2020 project MERLIN (grant agreement No. 101036337) reported by case studies till end of May 2025 for the Biodiversity Net gain criterion.	638.00 KB	10.5281/zenodo.17119733
Impact monitoring raw data reported by case studies in MERLIN (EU Horizon 2020) - Climate regulation	This dataset contains csv files with raw data of the impact monitoring within the EU Horizon 2020 project MERLIN (grant agreement No. 101036337) reported by case studies till end of May 2025 for the Climate regulation criterion.	80.81 KB	10.5281/zenodo.17119850
Impact monitoring raw data reported by case studies in MERLIN (EU Horizon 2020) - Flood resilience	This dataset contains csv files with raw data of the impact monitoring within the EU Horizon 2020 project MERLIN (grant agreement No. 101036337) reported by case studies till end of May 2025 for the Flood resilience criterion.	75.50 KB	10.5281/zenodo.17119895
Impact monitoring raw data reported by case studies in MERLIN (EU Horizon 2020) - Drought resilience	This dataset contains csv files with raw data of the impact monitoring within the EU Horizon 2020 project MERLIN (grant agreement No. 101036337) reported by case studies till end of May 2025 for the Drought resilience criterion.	70.82 KB	10.5281/zenodo.17119954
Impact monitoring raw data reported by case studies in MERLIN (EU Horizon 2020) - Health and well-being	This dataset contains csv files with raw data of the impact monitoring within the EU Horizon 2020 project MERLIN (grant agreement No. 101036337) reported by case studies till end of May 2025 for the Health and well-being criterion.	46.60 KB	10.5281/zenodo.17119982
Impact monitoring raw data reported by case studies in MERLIN (EU Horizon 2020) - Zero pollution	This dataset contains csv files with raw data of the impact monitoring within the EU Horizon 2020 project MERLIN (grant agreement No. 101036337) reported by case studies till end of May 2025 for the Zero pollution criterion.	189.76 KB	10.5281/zenodo.17120025

Impact monitoring raw data reported by case studies in MERLIN (EU Horizon 2020) - Farm to fork	This dataset contains csv files with raw data of the impact monitoring within the EU Horizon 2020 project MERLIN (grant agreement No. 101036337) reported by case studies till end of May 2025 for the Farm to fork criterion.	127.36 KB	10.5281/zenodo.17120070
Impact monitoring raw data reported by case studies in MERLIN (EU Horizon 2020) - Sustainable energy	This dataset contains csv files with raw data of the impact monitoring within the EU Horizon 2020 project MERLIN (grant agreement No. 101036337) reported by case studies till end of May 2025 for the Sustainable energy criterion.	13.53 KB	10.5281/zenodo.17120114
Impact monitoring raw data reported by case studies in MERLIN (EU Horizon 2020) - Sustainable transport	This dataset contains csv files with raw data of the impact monitoring within the EU Horizon 2020 project MERLIN (grant agreement No. 101036337) reported by case studies till end of May 2025 for the Sustainable transport criterion.	45.63 KB	10.5281/zenodo.17120150
Impact monitoring raw data reported by case studies in MERLIN (EU Horizon 2020) - Inclusive participation and governance	This dataset contains csv files with raw data of the impact monitoring within the EU Horizon 2020 project MERLIN (grant agreement No. 101036337) reported by case studies till end of May 2025 for the Inclusive participation and governance criterion.	175.12 KB	10.5281/zenodo.17120183
Impact monitoring raw data reported by case studies in MERLIN (EU Horizon 2020) - Circular economy	This dataset contains csv files with raw data of the impact monitoring within the EU Horizon 2020 project MERLIN (grant agreement No. 101036337) reported by case studies till end of May 2025 for the Circular economy criterion.	12.83 KB	10.5281/zenodo.17120221
Impact monitoring raw data reported by case studies in MERLIN (EU Horizon 2020) - Financing the transition	This dataset contains csv files with raw data of the impact monitoring within the EU Horizon 2020 project MERLIN (grant agreement No. 101036337) reported by case studies till end of May 2025 for the Financing the transition criterion.	64.34 KB	10.5281/zenodo.17120279
Impact monitoring raw data reported by case studies in MERLIN (EU Horizon 2020) - Green growth	This dataset contains csv files with raw data of the impact monitoring within the EU Horizon 2020 project MERLIN (grant agreement No. 101036337) reported by case studies till end of May 2025 for the Green growth criterion.	63.98 KB	10.5281/zenodo.17120323

3 Outlook

We provide a DOI for each of the 14 individual data products in the MERLIN Database of assessments of implementation and impact indicators, allowing integrity in citation tracking in their use beyond the project lifetime. This will support:

- Future retrieval, analysis, or other use of the data beyond the lifetime of the project.
- Use in new analyses of restoration effectiveness by the MERILN Project Community and other interested parties.